

Synthesizing computed tomography for radiotherapy: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Synthesizing computed tomography for radiotherapy

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

SynthRAD2025

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Clinical problem

Medical imaging has become increasingly important in the diagnosis and treatment of oncological patients, particularly in radiotherapy (RT), which is used in more than half of all cancer patients. In RT, pre-treatment imaging is used to develop a radiation treatment plan, which is subsequently delivered in fractions over up to 30 days. Traditionally, X-ray-based imaging is widely adopted in RT for patient positioning and monitoring before, during, or after the treatment, however, also magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is playing an increasingly indispensable role in radiotherapy workflows.

More specifically, accurately calculating radiation therapy doses for cancer patients requires detailed information about tissue photon attenuation or proton stopping power, traditionally obtained from computed tomography (CT) images. Ideally, this would be done at each treatment fraction. However, CT exposes patients to ionizing radiation, has a limited soft-tissue contrast and is usually not available in treatment rooms.

Opportunities

(1) MRI: Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) offers superb soft-tissue contrast without radiation but lacks the attenuation/stopping power data needed for radiation therapy dose calculation and treatment plan optimization [Schmidt et al., 2015].

(2) CBCT: Cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) is widely used in radiation therapy for in-room patient positioning and monitoring. However, its image quality is limited due to artifacts, hindering widespread adoption of in-room CBCT-based treatment planning [Boda-Heggeman J et al., 2011].

Solution Gap

Converting both MRI and CBCT to synthetic CT (sCT) images enables [Spadea 2021] (1) MRI-only radiation therapy, which minimizes radiation exposure, eliminates treatment inaccuracies due to CT-to-MRI registration errors and simplifies clinical workflows [Edmund and Nyholm, 2017] and (2) online adaptive MRI- or CBCT-based radiation therapy, where sCTs from either MRI or CBCT images allow for accurate dose calculations and daily treatment plan adaptation (at each fraction) to anatomical changes during therapy.

Justification

Publicly available datasets and challenges are needed to compare and advance sCT generation methods for both MRI and CBCT. This will ultimately lead to safer, more efficient, and potentially personalized radiation therapy for cancer patients.

Objective & Tasks

This challenge aims to provide a platform offering public data and evaluation metrics to compare the latest developments in sCT generation methods. A type 2 challenge will be run, where the participants need to submit their algorithm packaged in a docker for testing. Two tasks are defined. Task 1 comprises MRI-to-sCT generation to facilitate MRI-only and MRI-based adaptive radiotherapy. Task 2 will focus on CBCT-to-sCT generation to facilitate CBCT-based adaptive radiotherapy.

Dataset & the challenge

A multi-center dataset is presented, balancing training, validation and test cases to evaluate the methods on different MRI and CBCT devices and sequences/acquisition settings for head-and-neck, thorax and abdomen cases. Currently, five centers (UMC Utrecht, UMC Groningen, Radboud Nijmegen, LMU University Hospital Munich and University Hospital Cologne) share data providing 65/10/25 (train/validation/test) MRI or CBCT and CT pairs per tumor entity of patients undergoing radiotherapy at the respective institute.

A total of 900-1200 paired MRI-CT and 1500 CBCT-CT sets is provided, along with a body mask that will be considered for evaluation and may be used for inference. The target CTs of the validation and test set will not be shared with the participants to avoid optimistic biases. Input data of the validation and test set will be accessible by the algorithm submitted by the participants, but not directly available to the teams, until the end of the challenge.

The challenge runs on <https://synthrad2025.grand-challenge.org/>, and the pre-processing and evaluation code used to rank the submissions based on image, geometric, and dose evaluations will be shared.

Challenge participants may choose to participate either in Task 1 or 2 or both. For each task, algorithms should be provided for all the anatomical sites. The participants may decide whether to provide one or more models per task. The center of origin of the data will not be disclosed at a case level.

The evaluation code used to rank the challenge is shared at <https://github.com/SynthRAD2025>. After completion, the leaderboard will remain open for submission, ensuring that future methods may still be evaluated up to 2030. We envision that this challenge will enable a fair and open evaluation of different approaches to synthetic CT generation from MRI and CBCT.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

medical imaging, magnetic resonance imaging, computed tomography, cone beam computed tomography, image synthesis, generative model, radiotherapy

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

N/A

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

N/A

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

The best-performing teams will present their algorithms in short talks at a dedicated event or workshop, according to MICCAI availability. Note that the event can also be held purely online if necessary. Alternatively, but not desired, we could align with one of the workshops, e.g. SASHIMI, and present the results of the challenge, as done in 2023.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

The challenge will start on March 1 (2025) and end on August 15, lasting about 24 weeks: 13 weeks of sole training, followed by 7+4 weeks of validation and 4 weeks of testing. The workshop related to the challenge should last half a day.

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

The expected number of participants is > 500, with about 50 teams participating. We expect participation at least from the ten best-ranked teams at MICCAI 2025, other participants teams, and other interested attendees at the workshop. The expected number of teams is based on the single-user participation collected for SynthRAD2023. We will contact the teams that participated at SynthRAD2023 again. SynthRAD2023 has been selected as best in physics during ESTRO2024 (May 2024), and it has been announced that SynthRAD2025 will be held in an audience of 7000 members of the society.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

A publication on the dataset will be released (as arXiv, if not fully published) along with the start of the challenge. After the challenge is run, we plan to coordinate a publication (overview paper) describing the challenge results as a paper in a peer-reviewed journal that summarizes the results and outcomes, similar to what has been done for SynthRAD2023 (<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2403.08447>). The leaderboard will remain open after the challenge for new submissions. When the challenge is closed, we will release the code to perform the planning.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The challenge is online. For training purposes, the computing environment is left to the participants. The algorithms will run on a common platform encompassing an AWS g4dn.2xlarge instance using a single GPU with 16 GB RAM, 8 cores CPU, and 32 GB RAM. The half-day workshop support is needed for projectors, speakers, and microphones. We wish to hold a hybrid workshop with all the presenters available on-site.

TASK 1: Task 1 - MRI-to-CT

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Current clinical radiotherapy workflows rely on the availability of CT scans for each patient for dose calculation during treatment planning. To this aim, the quantitative CT numbers are converted to electron density (photon radiotherapy) or relative stopping power (proton radiotherapy). Besides CT, MRI is increasingly important as an additional imaging modality in radiotherapy. One main reason is the improved soft-tissue contrast of MRI with respect to CT, enabling more accurate identification and delineation of the tumor and critical organs at risk. These are crucial inputs for treatment plan optimization, next to the electron density or relative stopping power maps derived from CT. Since the imaging contrast in MRI is related to nuclear spin relaxation processes, there is no direct correlation of the MRI signal to the underlying quantities related to photon absorption or proton stopping in matter. Thus, MRI cannot be directly used for radiotherapy dose calculation.

Recently, however, there has been a substantially increasing interest in using MR images directly for dose calculation in radiotherapy workflows. The two main fields addressed in current research and seeing recent clinical adoption are MRI-only radiotherapy (workflow relying solely on MRI and not on CT), where usually diagnostic MRI scanners (1.5 T to 3 T magnetic field strength) are used for image acquisition before treating patients at conventional linear accelerators. MR-guided radiotherapy combines MRI linear accelerator hybrid devices (MR-Linacs, field strengths of 0.35 T or 1.5 T) for joint imaging and irradiation. Converting MRI to synthetic CT images for dose calculation and treatment plan optimization is critical in both cases. Ideally, CT acquisition could be made redundant, streamlining clinical workflows (only single planning imaging session), increasing patient throughput, reducing patient imaging dose, and eradicating possible systematic errors from incorrect CT-to-MRI alignment.

While there is a range of scientific contributions to synthetic CT generation from MRI using various AI tools, systematic comparison of novel deep learning approaches on common data sets still needs to be included. This is where SynthRAD2025, as a challenge, will be positioned by providing a publicly available dataset covering a range of the most challenging body regions (head and neck, thorax and abdomen) and various MRI scanners for data acquisition. Together with thorough algorithm evaluation through image, anatomy, and dose-based metrics, covering all relevant aspects in the scope of radiotherapy, SynthRAD2025 has the potential to move the field of AI-based synthetic CT generation forward substantially. In the long term, we envision identifying the most robust and accurate algorithms suitable for the task and guiding the radiotherapy field toward synthetic CT approaches that can eventually be safely implemented in radiotherapy practice. This will boost the efficiency of patient treatments in MRI-only and MR-guided radiotherapy workflows.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

medical imaging, magnetic resonance imaging, computed tomography, image synthesis, generative model, radiotherapy

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Adrian Thummerer LMU University Hospital Munich
 Arhur Jr. Galapon UMC Groningen
 Christopher Kurz LMU University Hospital Munich
 Erik van der Bijl Radboud UMC Nijmegen
 Florian Kamp University Hospital Cologne
 Guillaume Landry LMU University Hospital Munich
 Maarten Terpstra UMC Utrecht
 Matteo Maspero UMC Utrecht
 Niklas Wahl DKFZ Heidelberg
 Viktor Rogowski Skane University Hospital/Lund University

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Matteo Maspero, Assistant professor, UMC Utrecht, Computational Imaging group, m.maspero@umcutrecht.nl / matteo.maspero.it@gmail.com.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with a fixed deadline but with an open leaderboard for submission that will have a post-challenge phase to provide a platform for continuous evaluation of the algorithms.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

We aim to present a report on the challenge to MICCAI 2025 and ESTRO, managing to reach both the developers` (MICCAI) and the end-users` (ESTRO) communities.

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://synthrad2025.grand-challenge.org> is already available, even if the website is not yet findable among the listed challenges until December 1st 2024.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Only fully automatic methods are allowed. Methods should be submitted as specified on the submission page. Inference should run on an AWS g4dn.2xlarge instance using a single GPU with 16 GB RAM, 8 cores CPU and 32 GB RAM. The maximum inference time to produce an sCT for a single case (one patient) is 15 minutes.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

The data used to train algorithms is restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data, which should be reported in the document describing the submitted method. Pre-trained models may NOT be used in the challenge to ensure fairness evaluating the methods proposed.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge if not listed among the organizers, contributors, or data providers and if they did not co-author any publication (accepted publication date) with the organizers in the timeframe 2022-09/2025-09; otherwise, they are not eligible for the prizes. The only exception is made for the co-authors of the SynthRAD2023 challenge report who were not organizers: these co-authors (not the old challenge organizers) are allowed to participate to the challenge and possibly be awarded (see the list at <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2403.08447>). Organizers, contributors, or data providers may not participate in the challenge.

The following four roles can be taken in the scope of the challenge:

- Organizers: Take care of challenge organization. They cannot participate in the challenge due to the possible access to data.
- Contributors: These are people who support the challenge organization but are not actively involved in it. They cannot participate in the challenge due to possible access to data.
- Data provider: Collect and provide data to the organizers, support the organizers in the organization without an active role, not involved in the decision-making. They cannot participate in the challenge and will be listed in the dataset publication.
- Participant: Participate in the challenge organized in teams of up to five people. They cannot be listed among the organizers, contributors, or data providers.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Each participant/team can only use one account to participate in the competition. Participants who use multiple accounts will be disqualified from the competition. Each team can comprise five participants, but the organizers reserve the right to reduce the number of co-authors of the top-performing teams to the challenge paper summarizing the results (see publication policy). Once a participant or a team submits, the submission or the team cannot withdraw from the challenge.

As further conditions for being awarded a prize, the best-performing teams must fulfill the following obligations:

- Present their method in person at the final event of the challenge at MICCAI 2025.
- Submit a paper reporting the details of the methods in a short or long LNCS format, following the checklist

provided on the submission page. Organizers reserve the right to exclude submissions lacking any of these reporting elements.

- Submit a form reporting the details of the algorithm after the test submission has been completed, as it will be provided by the organizers.
 - Sign and return all prize acceptance documents as may be required by the Competition Sponsor/Organizers.
 - Commit to citing the data challenge paper and the data overview paper whenever submitting the developed method for scientific and non-scientific publications.
 - The top three teams in each task must disclose and openly share their code, weights, or models to allow for future re-use of their algorithms. The model can also be shared as a Docker version without sharing the code. While all other teams are strongly encouraged to do so, it is not mandatory. The code or Docker image should be provided within 14 days of the announcement of the winning participant.
- Depending on the available funding, organizers reserve the possibility of awarding cash prizes to the top teams for both tasks. The SynthRAD2025 organizers will consolidate the results and submit a challenge paper to Medical Image Analysis or similar. The first ten teams of each task will be invited to participate in this publication, requiring them to submit an algorithm summary in the requested form. The organizers reserve the right to reduce the number of co-authors among the team participants to at least two.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The results and winner will be announced publicly via the challenge website, and the top teams will be invited to present their approach during the final MICCAI event.

Once participants submit their results on the test set to the challenge organizers via the challenge website, they will be considered fully vested in the challenge so that their performance results will become part of presentations, publications, or subsequent analyses derived from the challenge at the organization's discretion. Specifically, all the performance results will be made public.

The SynthRAD2025 organizers will consolidate the results and submit a challenge paper to Medical Image Analysis (or similar).

Each team ranked among the top ten metrics will be invited to participate in this publication, requiring that they submit an algorithm summary in the form of LNCS proceedings. The organizers will analyze their sCT as the challenge submission system will have automatically solicited them.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

To be eligible for the official ranking, the participants must submit a paper describing their method as described in the Participation Policy, point d. The organizers, contributors, and data providers can independently publish methods based on the challenge data after an embargo of 6 months from the challenge's final event. The embargo is counted from the final event, considering the submission date of the work. Participants can submit their results elsewhere after an embargo of 6 months; however, if they cite the overview paper, no embargo will

be applied.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Submission instructions will be available on the challenge website.

We will organize a type 2 challenge, where algorithm submissions run through the website during the test phase, as described in <https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/challenges/>. Training data (MRI or CBCT and corresponding CT) will be publicly available. Input validation data (only MRI or CBCT) will be available to provide predictions after upload on the site (so type 1 is used for validation). During the test phase, the teams must supply the algorithm for the type 2 challenge to the organizers following the submission link and instructions provided on <https://synthrad2025.grand-challenge.org/>. Teams will submit their dockerized sCT algorithms to the challenge website without having the test data at their disposal. Once the challenge is presented at MICCAI, a post-challenge phase will be opened, making the validation and test phases newly available.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

The challenge is subdivided into a validation and test phase. The validation phase allows each team to submit up to 3 weekly submissions to familiarize themselves with the submission system and compare their performance with the intermediate results of other teams. All the submissions will be visible in the validation. The results of the validation phase will be evaluated on the validation set with an open dashboard.

The validation phase will remain open also during the test phase; in the last 4 weeks of the challenge, the test (final submission) phase will start. The validation phase will last 7 plus 4 weeks and take place for 13 weeks after the release of the data to allow development and training of the algorithms. After the validation phase, a new leaderboard will be created, and the type 2 test phase will start. During this final test phase, all data and targets remain hidden, requiring teams to upload their dockerized algorithms. At the end of the test phase, top-performing teams will be invited to present their methods.

The participating teams can submit up to two runs to evaluate their algorithms on the test set. The second run is granted to accommodate possible errors during the submission process. Only the last run will be counted for the official ranking of the teams and the challenge results. We request that each run will be identified with a description. To ensure no error occurs during the submission process, we will also set up a preliminary test phase (in parallel to the 11-week validation phase). In this test phase, participants can familiarize themselves with the submission system and test whether their dockerized algorithms run on a subset of the validation patients. Furthermore, we plan to send warnings when the submission format is incorrect, or performance is below a (very low) threshold, suggesting errors. We keep the test phase relatively short (4 weeks) to ensure teams have enough time to refine their methods.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge website open 1/12/2024

Start challenge: Release training cases 1/03/2025

Training phase (13+7+4 weeks) 1/03/2025 - 15/08/2025

Preliminary test phase (7+4 weeks, 5 submissions/week) 1/06/2025 - 15/08/2025

Validation phase (7+4 weeks, 3 submissions/week) 1/06/2025 - 15/08/2025

Presentation of the challenge at ESTRO2025 2/05/2025 - 6/05/2025

Test phase (4 weeks, max 2 submissions) 16/07/2023 - 15/08/2023

Announcements and invitation to present 10/09/2025

Presentation of the challenge results MICCAI25, South Korea, 6-10/10/2025 + ESTRO April/May 2026

Post-challenge phase (4.5 years, 2 submissions/60 days) 1/09/2025-1/03/2030

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Each institution is providing data requesting ethics approval by the internal review board/Medical Ethical committee (METC) of its institute:

- UMC Utrecht approved a non-WMO request on 4/03/2022 with number 22/474 entitled: `Synthesizing computed tomography for radiotherapy Grand Challenge (SynthRAD)`. Contact persons: Department of Radiotherapy, University Medical Center Utrecht, m.maspero@umcutrecht.nl; trialburauoncancercenter@umcutrecht.nl.
- UMC Groningen has submitted a non-WMO request entitled: `Synthesizing computed tomography for radiotherapy - Grand Challenge` Contact persons: Department of Radiation Oncology, University Medical Center Groningen a.v.galapon@umcg.nl / s.both@umcg.nl.
- Radboudumc UMC declared the study entitled `Synthesizing computed tomography for radiotherapy Grand Challenge` Contact persons: Department of Radiation Oncology, Radboud University Medical Center Nijmegen, erik.vanderbijl@radboudumc.nl.
- The LMU University Hospital Munich ethics committee approved a corresponding clinical study entitled `Generating synthetic computed tomography scans for radiotherapy: SynthRAD2025 challenge` on 15/04/2024 (study number 24-0195).
- University Hospital Cologne is undergoing METC approval.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Data is released under CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial). Each institution may decide whether to use the NC attribution.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Organizers' evaluation code and supporting data pre/post-processing code will be publicly available on GitHub at the following location: <https://github.com/SynthRAD2025>

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Openly sharing teams' code or docker is strongly encouraged but remains optional for all teams except for the three winning teams of each task. The code should be provided within 14 days of the announcement of the winning participants.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Sponsoring/ funding the challenge: ESTRO (European society), DGMP (German Society), NVFK (Dutch Society), and the Swedish Society of Radiation Physics endorsed the challenge. Grants have received from LMU University Hospital Munich. Additional funding was discussed with commercial parties, but no confirmed participation was ensured when this file was submitted. Further funding will be openly disclosed.

Access to the test case labels: data providers have access to the test case target and have provided the data to the organizers. The test cases will be accessed during the preparation of the test phase by the organizers.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education

- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Radiotherapy/radiation oncology, Intervention assistance, Intervention planning, Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Synthesis (image), Regression (image)

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The biomedical application addressed patients undergoing radiotherapy (about 50% of cancer patients). We will collect data randomly sampling cases of both sexes, ensuring a balanced representation of sexes. A

predominantly adult population would be collected. Inclusion criteria would be the acquisition of CT and MRI during treatment planning and for online adaptive MRI-guided treatment (task 1) or CT and in-room CBCT (task 2) to ensure accurate positioning during image-guided and enable CBCT-guided adaptive radiotherapy. MRI and CBCT should be acquired within two months of the CT to reduce anatomical changes.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Patients undergoing radiotherapy in the head and neck, thorax, and abdomen will be considered for both tasks. For task 1, patients should have undergone MRI and CT acquisition. For task 2, patients should have undergone CBCT and CT imaging. The cohort collected for the challenge is a subsample of the target cohort in the final biomedical application. For privacy purposes, the face of the head-and-neck cases has been removed consistently on the whole dataset. Face removal is the only deviation from the final biomedical application.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI, CT

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

We provide the acquisition parameters for the training set for all the imaging modalities. Moreover, a mask of the body contour is provided to calculate part of the metrics. Participants may be able to discriminate the anatomical regions between head and neck, abdomen or thorax cases via a provided label, but not able to discriminate between center of origin.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Age and sex will be provided for the centers from which sharing such demographic details has been granted.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Head and neck, abdomen, and thorax images from patients undergoing radiotherapy.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithms should target all the anatomical regions mentioned above (head and neck, thorax, and abdomen). However, the area surrounding the tumors (up to the skin) will be most relevant, given that the irradiation needs to traverse the whole body to reach the tumor. Participants may be able to discriminate the anatomical regions among head and neck, abdomen or thorax cases via a provided label, but not able to discriminate between center of origin.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Find an algorithm that generates sCTs that are similar to CT images (image similarity metrics), geometrically accurate (geometry metric(s)) and that can be used for the downstream task of radiotherapy planning (dose metrics).

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

CT and MRI were acquired on the following devices:

At Center A, MRIs for head-and-neck, thorax and abdomen were acquired on Philips Ingenia 1.5/3T scanners, while corresponding CTs were acquired on Philips Brilliance Big Bore (all anatomical regions) or Siemens Biograph 20 PET-CT (head-and-neck only) scanners.

At Center B, MRIs were acquired with Siemens MAGNETOM Aera or Avanto_fit 1.5T scanners and CTs were acquired with Siemens SOMATOM Definition AS scanners.

Center C used a Siemens Avanto FIT 1.5T (head-and-neck) or an Elekta Unity 1.5T MR-Linac (Thorax and Abdomen) for MR acquisitions and Philips Brilliance Big Bore or Siemens Somatom Go.Open Pro for CTs

At Center D MRIs were acquired using a ViewRay MRIdian 0.35T MR-Linac (Abdomen, Lung) and CTs using a TOSHIBA Aquilion/LB CT scanner.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

All images were acquired with the clinically used imaging protocols of the respective centers for each anatomical site and reflect typical images found in daily clinical routine. Due to different clinical routines, imaging protocols for MRI and CT vary within and between centers, which reflects a realistic application scenario. A detailed table of imaging parameters will be distributed with the dataset.

At Center A, head-and-neck MRI images were acquired with a T1 3D spoiled gradient-recalled echo (GRE) sequence with Gadolinium contrast, and thorax/abdomen images with a T1 3D VANE Dixon (in-phase) or T1 3D GRE Dixon (in-phase) sequence.

At Center B, head-and-neck MRIs were acquired with a T1w-VIBE DIXON sequence, thorax and abdomen MRIs with T1w-VIBE or T2w TSE.

Center C used a T1 turbo spin echo (TSE) for head-and-neck, and T1w-VIBE fat saturated for thorax and abdomen

patients.

Center D used a 3D balanced steady state free-precession sequence (bSSFP) for thorax and abdomen MRIs in breath hold.

Note that after data collection, the data acquisition protocol may slightly vary from the one here specified, especially for the centers that have not yet METC approval, and for whom the whole dataset is not fully available yet.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data was acquired for radiotherapy treatments in the radiotherapy departments of UMC Utrecht, UMC Groningen, Radboud UMC and LMU Munich and was not provided in any previous challenge. The challenge participants will not be able to recognize the center of origin since the data are anonymized and the institution's names are substituted with institute identifiers A, B, C and D.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data was acquired by the clinical staff of the respective radiotherapy departments. All patients were treated with external beam radiotherapy in the head-and-neck, thorax, or abdomen region. The clinically used delineation of target structures and organs-at-risk of patients in the test set will be prepared internally for evaluation purposes (e.g., dose evaluation).

Each center may have different routines concerning the patients` positioning in CT and MRI (e.g., different immobilization devices such as masks or vacuum cushions, use of flat table tops) and might follow their delineation guidelines.

Details about data characteristics for each anatomical site and center will be reported in an upcoming publication focusing on the dataset. Along with the challenge, a pre-print (or, if time allows, a publication) will be released.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Definition of a case:

A case refers to a single patient consisting of a CT and an MRI of the same patient and a patient outline mask. Radiotherapy treatment plans and structure sets (target volume and organs-at-risk) are also available for test cases.

A train case contains an input image (MRI for task 1) and a corresponding reference (CT), while a validation and test case only has an input MRI. Test inputs will not be publicly available until the challenge is fully closed.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Data for Task 1 will be provided by UMC Utrecht, UMC Groningen, Radboud UMC, and LMU Munich. Due to variations in data availability, the dataset size might vary between anatomical regions and centers. The targeted dataset split is 65% training, 10% validation, and 25% testing.

Head-and-Neck:

Center A: 100 - 150

Center B: 100

Center C: 100 - 150

Center D: 0 (unavailable)

Total: 300 - 400 (260 training, 40 validation, 100 testing)

Thorax:

Center A: 100 - 150

Center B: 50 - 100

Center C: 50 - 100

Center D: 100

Total: 300 - 400 (195 - 260 training, 30 - 40 validation, 75 - 100 testing)

Abdomen:

Center A: 100 - 150

Center B: 50 - 100

Center C: 50 - 100

Center D: 100

Total: 300 - 400 (195 - 260 training, 30 - 40 validation, 75 - 100 testing)

In total, Task 1 will consist of 900 to 1200 cases (300-400 for each anatomical region) from which 585 - 780 will be used for training, 90 - 120 for validation, and 225 - 300 for testing. The final amount of cases is not yet available due to the ongoing data collection at data providing institutions.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The amount of data and the split into training/validation and testing sets is based on previous studies in the field (see the review article by Spadea and Maspero et al., 2021), which considered, on average, between 30-50 patients for a single anatomy. In our dataset, we have significantly increased that amount for each single center, where -when available- we included around 100 patients per anatomy. Moreover, compared to our previous SynthRAD2023 challenge, with SynthRAD2025, we increased the number of anatomical regions from two to three and the number of patients per center and anatomy from 90 to 100. The SynthRAD2025 dataset is the largest public dataset dedicated to research into synthetic CT generation in head-and-neck, thorax, and abdomen patients.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The inclusion criteria for the SynthRAD2025 dataset were relatively loose, with the only requirement being that patients were treated with some form of radiotherapy in one of the three anatomical regions (head-and-neck, thorax, and abdomen). The imaging protocol varies within and across data-providing centers, representing the

clinical routine where many imaging protocols are used clinically. We did not select patients based on certain tumor characteristics, and the dataset represents a random sample of clinical routine. However, since we are performing a dose evaluation, we might include or exclude certain patients from the test set, to allow for meaningful dose calculation (e.g., in case of large anatomical changes between MRI and reference CT image).

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

N/A

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

No annotations were made, and no annotators can be considered given that the task is regression. No manual interaction was performed on the provided data.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Not applicable

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not applicable

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not applicable

Other annotations used for the evaluation: Imaging protocols will be provided on a per-patient basis in Excel files, reporting each imaging modality's relevant acquisition and reconstruction settings.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Data pre-processing includes the following steps:

Image conversion: All images are converted to the compressed .mha file format.

Field-of-view masking: A field-of-view mask of the input MRI will be generated.

Image registration: A rigid image registration between MR (task 1) and CT will be performed for all cases to align the images (using Elastix: <https://elastix.lumc.nl/index.php>). Participants can further improve the registration (rigid and deformable) if required. Elastix parameter files will be made available for participants for rigid registration, and a suggestion will be provided for deformable registration.

Defacing: Face removal/de-identification will be performed for head-and-neck patients using an in-house developed defacing algorithm.

Image resampling: All images will be resampled to a uniform voxel spacing per anatomical site: 1x1x3 mm³ for abdomen and thorax, and for head-and-neck it may be considered a voxel spacing between 1x1x2 and 1x1x3 mm³ corresponding to the most frequent slice spacing in the CT images.

Image masking: The patient outline will be automatically segmented based on the input image (MRI) using thresholding and morphological operations. The resulting mask will be dilated to include some surrounding air. In some patients with low MR intensities at the superior and inferior field-of-view border the mask is corrected by cropping the first and last 10 slices in the superior-inferior direction. The mask will be provided to participants and can be used if needed, for pre-processing. During evaluation, metrics will be calculated using this mask whenever specified.

Image cropping: To reduce the file sizes, all images will be cropped to the bounding box of the patient outline with an added margin of 20 voxels whenever the image dimensions allow it.

Additional pre-processing is performed for the validation and test set to enable calculation of metrics (image similarity, segmentation, and only for the test set the dose calculation):

Deformable image registration: Images are deformably registered using the open-source B-spline deformable image registration (DIR) algorithm implemented in Elastix. This minimizes differences due to anatomical changes or positioning. DIR parameter files are openly available to participants as part of the pre-processing tools.

Stitching: Due to the sometimes limited field-of-view of MRI we will stitch parts of the deformed CT outside the MR field-of-view. This is required to perform meaningful dose calculations. However, all metrics will only be calculated for the original input image field-of-view and not the entire stitched image.

The code for all pre-processing steps will be publicly available at our GitHub repository (<https://github.com/SynthRAD2025/preprocessing>)

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Not applicable, no annotation performed.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Input images (MRI) and the corresponding reference CT images are acquired with various time delays, which can cause differences in anatomy. Furthermore, slightly different patient positioning also introduces differences between input and reference images. To mitigate this, we perform a rigid image registration to match the two images (CT-MRI) as well as possible in the training data, but residual registration errors are unavoidable.

Air moves around the abdomen, and bladder/intestine filling can change. There is no exact way to correct this, representing a limitation of the SynthRAD2025 dataset. Note also that MRI is affected by geometric distortions, which may result in smaller body contours than on the reference CTs. We will apply deformable registration during evaluation (validation and test) to mitigate residual registration errors. If a model has learned to correct consistent differences in the input images (MRI and CT), the algorithm may underperform in the validation/test set.

Furthermore, due to the varying availability of data for each modality, center, and anatomical region, the dataset may not be fully balanced among centers/protocols. Some centers use similar imaging protocols or devices for some modalities or anatomical regions, while for other sites, there is even variation within single centers, further impacting the data balancing.

Note that all challenge participants will deal with the same dataset, so the evaluation is deemed unbiased, even though some teams may develop methods less sensitive to registration and geometric mismatches.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

N.B. due to the limited formatting, the equation and dose constraints have been omitted in this sections, but are available in the supplementary material.

The output sCT will be compared to the CT undergoing an image similarity (validation and test phase), geometric fidelity (validation and test phase) and a dose evaluation (test phase only due to heavy computational costs). For all analyses, to ensure maximal anatomical similarity between the sCT and the ground truth CT, the latter will be deformed by deformable image registration using an open-source deformable image registration algorithm (e.g. Elastix toolbox or plastimatch) as described above in the dataset section.

Image evaluation between the sCT and CT using the metrics listed below:

- Mean absolute error (MAE) in the mask.
- Peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) in the mask.
- Multi-scale structural similarity index (MS-SSIM) in the mask.

Geometric consistency between CT and sCT will be evaluated by analyzing the segmentation of anatomical structures. The images will be segmented using deep learning-based image segmentation solutions (TotalSegmentator). The geometric consistency will be evaluated using the: multiclass-DICE coefficient (mDice) and the 95th percentile Hausdorff distance (HD95), averaging over all the structures. The HD95 is similar to the Hausdorff distance, but is obtained by computing the 95th percentile of the distances between the boundaries rather than the maximum. This metric is more robust against outlier segmentations.

TotalSegmentator will be used to provide segmentations in the abdomen and thorax region using the liver, kidney, lung, ribs, sternum, vertebrae, myocardium, cardiac ventricles, and cardiac atria structures. Moreover, TotalSegmentator will be used to provide segmentations in the head-and-neck regions using the brainstem, spinal cord, skull, vertebrae, submandibles, parotid glands, thyroid, esophagus, trachea, and oral cavity structures.

Dose evaluation will be performed globally and locally by comparing photon and proton dose calculations between reference CT and sCT. Clinically, the most relevant question would be how a dose plan optimized on the CT (the 'ground truth' currently used for patient treatment) would perform on the sCT (the image at the disposal in the new clinical workflow). Dose calculations and optimization will be performed with matRad

(<https://e0404.github.io/matRad/>), an open-source treatment planning system where photon and proton intensity-modulated treatment plans will be optimized on the reference CT. Dose prescriptions and plans will be chosen irrespective of the original clinical goal for each anatomy, with the center of the planning target volume (PTV) chosen as the isocenter. Specifically, we will prescribe to the target (PTV) 30x2.0 Gy for the head and neck, 35x2.0 Gy for the lung, and 30x2.0 Gy for the abdomen at the 95% isodose level for both photons and protons. For simplicity, proton plans will be planned using the same PTV approach as photons, without robust optimization. Dose delivery will be simulated via ten beams of 6MV for photons using the generic Linac model and 2-3 beams for proton plans using the generic proton system modeled in matRad. The number and direction of beams may be optimized on a patient basis to comply with the dose prescription and limit the dose to the organs-at-risk (OARs) following the international guidelines: for the head and neck [Deasy et al., 2010, Beetz et al, 2013 and Marks et al, 2010], lung [Puckett et al., 2023] and the abdomen [Marks et al, 2010]. To further reduce the dose to the healthy tissues and ensure plan uniformity between patients, we will use the same objective functions and constraints available in matRad per treatment site, as reported in Table 1 (presented in the attachment to the submission). OARs dose limits will be handled as hard constraints whenever possible but might be turned into objectives on a patient-specific basis.

For each sCT, the plan optimized on the reference CT will be recalculated without replanning to avoid possible differences due to plan optimization.

The following metrics are considered for this aspect of the evaluation:

- Mean absolute dose differences relative to the prescribed dose $D_{\text{prescribed}}$ as described by MAE_target dose in the region with D greater equal than 90% of $D_{\text{prescribed}}$ of the (synthetic) CT.
- A dose-volume histogram (DVH) provides information on the delivered dose subvolumes of specific structures. Small differences in DVH parameters between the CT and the sCT indicate a good radiotherapy treatment based on the sCT. We consider four DVH parameters: near-minimum dose to the target ($D_{98\% \text{target}}$), which is the dose that at least 98% of the target volume received, $V_{95\% \text{target}}$, which is the target volume that received at least 95% of the prescribed dose, near-maximum dose to OARs ($D_{2\% \text{OAR}}$), which is the dose 2% of the volume of a specific organ-at-risk (OAR) received, and D_{meanOAR} , which is the mean dose a specific OAR received. Specifically, using the near-minimum and near-maximum was suggested by ICRU83 (<https://www.fnkv.cz/soubory/216/icru-83.pdf>). For the evaluation, we recognize the three OARs closest to the target (PTV) per region. To obtain one metric for all DVH parameters, we sum the relative absolute differences of the above mentioned parameters between the CT and sCT. The final metric is defined as the sum of the difference of each DVH metric over the three closest OARs.
- Gamma index: The Gamma pass ratios will be calculated for sCTs doses using the CT doses as a reference. The calculation is performed in 3D, according to Low et al., 1998. The passing criteria are the dose-difference criterion = 2% and the distance-to-agreement criterion = 2mm.

Gamma pass rates will be calculated within the regions that receive at dose higher than 10% of $D_{\text{prescribed}}$, based on the dose calculation of the CT, as suggested by Ezzel et al., 2009.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Image similarity: MAE, PSNR, and MS-SSIM are image similarity metrics commonly used in medical image synthesis. For a detailed overview, see the review by Spadea and Maspero et al., 2021. The MS-SSIM was chosen over the SSIM to provide image similarity information both on a global (general contrast and noise level) and a local level (similarity of the tumor and organs-at-risk on a pixel level).

Geometric consistency: This metric ensures that the sCT anatomically corresponds to the content of the CT. This

objective is paramount in adaptive radiotherapy and provides insights beyond image similarity metrics. This ensures that anatomical structures can be delineated accurately on sCT and increases clinical confidence in the output of the models.

Relative dose differences: This metric provides insight into the dose distribution in the local regions that receive a high dose. Only including these regions ensures that the large regions receiving little to almost no dose do not unintentionally determine the outcome of this metric.

DVH parameters: In radiotherapy, DVH parameters are commonly used to assess dose distributions in target volumes and OARs [Drzymala et al., 1991]. Specifically, DVH parameters describe target coverage and OAR sparing. Considering differences in the DVH parameters is a way of verifying that clinically relevant objectives are maintained.

Gamma index: This is a commonly used metric in radiotherapy to compare two dose distributions. It combines dose difference criteria and distance difference criteria in a single metric. Low et al., 1998 describe the details of the theoretical background. The medical physicist association suggests using 3%,3mm distance-to-agreement criteria when comparing delivered and planned doses [Ezzel et al., 2009]. We will adopt an even more stringent criterion (2%, 2mm), considering that error in the planning phase lead to irradiating the patient with a systematically deviating dose from the planned one.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

A water bulk-assigned baseline sCT model will be used as a submission threshold. The water sCTs will be obtained by assigning 0 HU to voxels (value of water by definition) within the dilated body contour mask and -1000 HU outside the mask (air).

Teams will not be considered in the ranking if their method does not outperform the water baseline in at least one of the three individual image similarity metrics.

To rank the submissions by the participants, the average metric value over all the patients is computed. Then, this average score is ranked per metric against all other submissions. The final rank for a submission is obtained by computing the average rank per metric, ranging from 1 (best submission) to n (worst submission). This RankThenMean approach is selected for SynthRAD2025, as opposed to MeanThenRank for SynthRAD2023, since the 2023 challenge report demonstrated that RankThenMean was stable without the need for arbitrary normalization of metrics (see <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2403.08447> sections 2.6 and 4.5)

Phase 1 = validation: The first ranking phase includes only the image metrics (3 = MAE, PSNR, SSIM) and geometry consistency (2 = DSC, HD95) on the validation set. The rank in the validation phase will be calculated using the RankThenMean procedure described above.

Phase 2 = test: The second-ranking phase includes the image metrics (3 = MAE, PSNR, SSIM), geometric consistency (2 = DSC, HD95) & the dose evaluation (3 for photon therapy and 3 for proton therapy) on the test set. First, the automatic ranking based on the image similarity metrics will be performed, as in Phase 1. Secondly, dose

evaluation will be run, and again the MAEtarget dose, DVHmetric and gamma index will be computed both for photon and proton plans. Dose evaluation depends on matRad, an open source fully validated treatment planning system written in Matlab. We will incorporate an automatic evaluation pipeline on the hosting site, offering dose evaluation for all the test submissions, along with a leaderboard. The ranking among all (11=3 image similarity, 2 geometric consistency, 6 dose) metrics will be determined according to the RankThenMean described procedure above. In case of a tie, the team with the best dose accuracy will rank higher than teams with an equal average rank. The proton dose accuracy will be ultimately decisive in case a tie will result from photon dose metrics.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

The submission platform will report the missing value if a team fails to submit sCTs for one or more patients in the validation phase. When a resubmission is still incomplete or corrupt, a black image (indicating an image that contains only air) will be used as an sCT of the specific patient. During the test, the dockerized algorithms must be submitted, so if the preliminary phase works, all the result cases must be present.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

- Ranking per metric is a transparent way to obtain the final ranking, preserving the strengths and weaknesses of a method, while placing equal weight on the importance of each metric.
- Aggregating and ranking were chosen to preserve large and small performance differences while combining metrics.
- After a previous investigation from SynthRAD2023 (see <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2403.08447> sections 2.6 and 4.5), the chosen method was the most stable one.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The variability of the ranking will be assessed with a Kendall's tau analysis. We will investigate whether including only the image, geometric consistency or the dose evaluation will lead to different rankings. Furthermore, the patterns of the different dose evaluations will also be analyzed.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Kendall's tau quantifies differences between rankings, which can provide insight into the quality of a metric.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or

- ranking variability.

We will categorize performances based on the participants' methods to generate the sCTs. This analysis will, for example, consider the difference between paired versus unpaired approaches and 2D versus 3D models. Furthermore, we will analyze the influence of the automated quantitative analysis on biases in our data and methods, considering, for example, the effect of registration and the difference in the quality of paired images for the head and neck, thorax and abdomen. Lastly, we will include qualitative analysis by expert observers on single cases, reporting their agreement on the quantitative analysis and their opinion on the sCT quality.

TASK 2: Task 2 - CBCT-to-CT

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

In radiotherapy, CBCT is by far the most widespread in-room imaging modality. In most cases, in-room CBCT images are solely used for patient alignment prior to irradiation, often relying on bony anatomy or fiducial markers. Ideally, the CBCT images would also be employed to adapt the patients' treatment plans daily to the patients' anatomy. This would allow to properly address interfractional anatomical changes as appearing, e.g., for the treatment sites considered for this challenge (head and neck, thorax and abdomen). In particular, treatment safety margins accounting for potential interfractional anatomical changes considered during treatment planning could be substantially reduced, opening options for increased tumor dose at lower burden to close-by organs at risk. This is hereby for a more efficient radiotherapeutic treatment of patients. However, in today's clinical practice, CBCT imaging quality is insufficient for accurate dose calculation and, thus, an adaptation of the in-room daily treatment plan. The reasons are mainly related to the design of the imaging systems, relying on photon detection with flat panel detectors, leading, among others, to the detection of a considerable amount of scattered photons.

While latest-generation devices largely account for these limitations by applying scatter-grids and advanced iterative image reconstruction techniques, including scatter estimates, these devices still need to become more widely available. A considerably larger benefit for a much bigger patient collective treated at conventional CBCT-equipped linear accelerators could be achieved by rendering CBCT images suitable for daily dose calculation by generating synthetic CTs from CBCT images of limited quality.

Many researchers have addressed this topic already; however, the comparability of algorithms suggested in the literature is heavily limited using different data sets and evaluation metrics in these studies. SynthRAD2025 addresses these shortcomings by providing a comprehensive data set for three of the most challenging treatment sites (head and neck, thorax, abdomen) acquired at different institutes with different CBCT devices and image acquisition settings. SynthRAD2025 aims to identify the most accurate and reliable AI solutions for synthetic CT generation from CBCT. This also includes systematic evaluation regarding all relevant radiotherapy-related metrics (image, anatomy, and dose-based). With this, we hope to pave the way towards clinical adoption of these algorithms to foster the widespread use of CBCT imaging systems for daily adaptive patient treatment.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

medical imaging, computed tomography, cone-beam computed tomography, image synthesis, generative model, radiotherapy

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

See task 1

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

See task 1

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

See task 1

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

See task 1

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

See task 1

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

See task 1

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

See task 1

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

See task 1

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

See task 1

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

See task 1

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

See task 1

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

See task 1

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

See task 1

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

See task 1

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

See task 1

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

See task 1

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

See task 1

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

See task 1

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

See task 1

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

See task 1

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning

- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

See task 1

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

See task 1

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

See task 1

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

See task 1

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

CBCT, CT

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

See task 1

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

See task 1

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

as for task 1

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

See task 1

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

See task 1

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

CT and CBCT were acquired on the following devices:

At Center A, B (abdomen only), C and D, CBCTs were acquired using an Elekta XVI on-board CBCT scanner. At

Center B CBCTs were acquired with an IBA Proteus Plus proton therapy gantry. At Center E, a Varian XI CBCT scanner was used. At Center A the corresponding CTs were acquired with a Philips Brilliance Big Bore or Siemens Biograph 20 PET-CT scanner (head-and-neck only), at Center B with a Siemens Definition AS, at Center C with a Philips Brilliance Big Bore or Siemens Somatom Go.Open Pro, at Center D and E with a TOSHIBA Aquilion/LB.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

All images were acquired with the clinically used imaging protocols of the respective centers for each anatomical site and reflect typical images found in daily clinical routines. Due to different clinical routines, imaging protocols for CBCT and CT vary within and between centers, which reflects a realistic application scenario. A detailed table of imaging parameters will be distributed with the dataset.

The CBCT image acquisition protocols varied between centers:

Center A used 100kV/10mA/20ms (head-and-neck), 120kV/16-32mA/20ms (thorax), 100-120kV/10-40mA/20-64ms (abdomen)

Center B used 100kV/160ma/12.5ms (head-and-neck), 110kV/320ma/12.5ms (thorax), 120kV/40ma/40ms (abdomen)

Center C used 120kV/10ma/20ms (head-and-neck), 120kV/10ma/20-40ms (thorax), 120kV/40ma/40ms (abdomen)

Center D used 100kV/10ma/10ms (head-and-neck), 120kV/40ma/40ms (thorax), 120kV/40ma/40ms (abdomen)

Center E used 125kV/20ma/40ms (head-and-neck), 125kV/20ma/40ms (thorax), 125kV/80ma/40ms (abdomen)

Note that after data collection, the data acquisition protocol may slightly vary from the one here specified, especially for the centers that have not yet received ethical approval, and for whom the whole dataset is not fully available yet. Also, the imaging protocol reported indicates the most common parameters.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data was acquired for radiotherapy treatments in the radiotherapy departments of UMC Utrecht, UMC Groningen, Radboud UMC, LMU Munich, and Uniklinik Cologne and was not provided in any previous challenge. The challenge participants will not be able to recognize the origin center since the data are anonymized and the institution's names are substituted with randomly provided institute identifiers A, B, C, D and E.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data was acquired by the clinical staff of the respective radiotherapy departments. All patients included were treated with some form of external beam radiotherapy in the head-and neck, thorax or abdomen region. The clinically used delineation of target structures and organs-at-risk of patients in the test set will be prepared internally for evaluation purposes (e.g dose evaluation).

Each center may have different routines concerning the patients` positioning in CT and CBCT (e.g., different immobilization devices such as masks or vacuum cushions, use of flat table tops) and might follow their delineation guidelines.

Details about data characteristics for each anatomical site and center will be reported in an upcoming publication focusing on the dataset. Along with the challenge, a pre-print (or, if time allows, a publication) will be released.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Definition of a case:

A case refers to a single patient consisting of a CT and a CBCT of the same patient and a patient outline mask. Radiotherapy treatment plans and structure sets (target volume and organs-at-risk) are also collected for test cases.

A train case contains an input image (CBCT for task 2) and a corresponding reference (CT), while a validation and test case only has an input CBCT. Test inputs will not be publicly available until the challenge is fully closed.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

UMC Utrecht, UMC Groningen, Radboud UMC, LMU Munich, and Uniklinik Cologne will provide data for Task 2. Each centre contributes 100 cases per anatomy, and the dataset will be split into 65% training, 10% validation, and 25% testing.

Head-and-Neck:

Center A: 100

Center B: 100

Center C: 100

Center D: 100

Center E: 100

Total: 500 (325 training, 50 validation, 125 testing)

Thorax:

Center A: 100

Center B: 100

Center C: 100

Center D: 100

Center E: 100

Total: 500 (325 training, 50 validation, 125 testing)

Abdomen:

Center A: 100

Center B: 100

Center C: 100

Center D: 100

Center E: 100

Total: 500 (325 training, 50 validation, 125 testing)

In total, Task 2 will consist of 1500 cases (500 for each anatomical region), of which 975 will be used for training, 150 for validation, and 375 for testing.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The amount of data and the split into training/validation and testing sets is based on previous studies in the field (see the review article by Spadea and Maspero et al., 2021), which considered, on average, between 30-50 patients for a single anatomy. In our dataset, we have significantly increased that amount for each single center, where -when available- we included around 100 patients per anatomy. Moreover, compared to our previous SynthRAD2023 challenge, with SynthRAD2025, we increased the number of anatomical regions from two to three and the number of patients per center and anatomy from 90 to 100. The SynthRAD2025 dataset is the largest public dataset dedicated to research into synthetic CT generation in head-and-neck, thorax, and abdomen patients.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The inclusion criteria for the SynthRAD2025 dataset were relatively loose, with the only requirement being that patients were treated with some form of radiotherapy in one of the three anatomical regions (head-and-neck, thorax, and abdomen). The imaging protocol varies within and across data-providing centers, representing the clinical routine where many imaging protocols are used clinically. We did not select patients based on certain tumor characteristics, and the dataset represents a random sample of clinical routine. However, since we are performing a dose evaluation, we might include or exclude certain patients from the test set, to allow for meaningful dose calculation (e.g., in case of large anatomical changes between CBCT and reference CT image).

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

N/A

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

No annotations were made, and no annotators can be considered given that the task is regression. No manual interaction was performed on the provided data.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Not applicable

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not applicable

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See Task 1

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Data pre-processing includes the following steps:

Image conversion: All images are converted to the compressed .mha file format.

Field-of-view masking: A field-of-view mask of the input CBCT will be generated.

Image registration: To align the images, a rigid image registration between CBCT (task 2) and CT will be performed for all cases (using Elastix: <https://elastix.lumc.nl/index.php>). Participants can further improve the registration (rigid and deformable) if required. Elastix parameter files will be made available for participants for rigid registration.

Defacing: Face removal/de-identification will be performed for head-and-neck patients using an in-house developed defacing algorithm.

Image resampling: All images will be resampled to a uniform voxel spacing per anatomical site: 1x1x3 mm³ for abdomen and thorax, and for head-and-neck it may be considered a voxel spacing between 1x1x2 and 1x1x3 mm³ corresponding to the most frequent slice spacing in the CT images.

Image masking: The patient outline will be automatically segmented based on the input image (CBCT) using thresholding and morphological operations. The resulting mask will be dilated to include some surrounding air. The mask will be provided to participants and can be used, if needed, for pre-processing. During evaluation image similarity and dose metrics will be calculated using this mask whenever specified.

Image cropping: To reduce the file sizes, all images will be cropped to the bounding box of the patient outline with an added margin of 20 voxels whenever the image dimensions allow it.

Additional pre-processing is performed for the validation and test set to enable calculation of metrics (image similarity, segmentation and only for the set test the dose calculation):

Deformable image registration: The Elastix B-spline open-source deformable image registration (DIR) algorithm will be used to deform CT images to the CBCT. This minimizes differences due to anatomical changes or positioning. Parameter file to perform DIR will be made available to participants as part of the pre-processing tools.

Stitching (only for the test set): Due to the sometimes limited field-of-view of CBCTs, we stitch parts of the deformed CT outside the CBCT field-of-view. This is required to perform meaningful dose calculations. However, all metrics will only be calculated for the original input image field-of-view and not the entire stitched image.

The code for all pre-processing steps will be publicly available at our GitHub repository (<https://github.com/SynthRAD2025/preprocessing>).

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Not applicable, no annotation performed.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Input images (CBCT) and the corresponding reference CT images are acquired with various time delays, which can cause differences in anatomy. Furthermore, slightly different patient positioning also introduces differences between input and reference images. To mitigate this, we perform a rigid image registration to match the two images as well as possible (CT-CBCT) in the training data, but residual registration errors are unavoidable. Air moves around the abdomen, and bladder/intestine filling can change. There is no exact way to correct this, representing a limitation of the SynthRAD2025 dataset. Note also that CBCT can be affected by cupping/saturation artifacts, which results in smaller body contours than on the reference CTs. We will apply deformable registration during evaluation (validation and test) to mitigate residual registration errors. If a model has learned to correct consistent differences in the input images (CBCT and CT), the algorithm may underperform in the validation/test set.

Furthermore, due to the varying availability of data for each modality, center, and anatomical region, the dataset may not be fully balanced among centers/protocols. Some centers use similar imaging protocols or devices for some modalities or anatomical regions, while for other sites, there is even variation within single centers, further impacting the data balancing.

Note that all challenge participants will deal with the same dataset, so the evaluation is deemed unbiased, even though some teams may develop methods less sensitive to registration and geometric mismatches.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

See task 1

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

See task 1

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

See task 1

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

See task 1

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

See task 1

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

See task 1

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

See task 1

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

See task 1

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

References relevant to the challenge design

Old challenge design of SynthRAD2023:

Adrian Thummerer, Evi Huijben, Maarten Terpstra, Oliver Gurney-Champion, Many Afonso, Suraj Pai, Peter Koopmans, Maureen van Eijnatten, Zoltan Perko, & Matteo Maspero. (2023). SynthRAD2023 Challenge design (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7746020>

Dataset of SynthRAD2023

Thummerer, A., van der Bijl, E., & Maspero, M. (2023). SynthRAD2023 Grand Challenge dataset: synthesizing computed tomography for radiotherapy (0.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7260705>

Publication related to the old dataset

Thummerer A, van der Bijl E, Galapon Jr A, Verhoeff JJ, Langendijk JA, Both S, van den Berg CN, Maspero M. SynthRAD2023 Grand Challenge dataset: Generating synthetic CT for radiotherapy. Medical physics. 2023

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Huijben E, Terpstra ML, Galapon Jr A, Pai S, Thummerer A, Koopmans P, Afonso M, van Eijnatten M, Gurney-Champion O, Chen Z, Zhang Y. Generating Synthetic Computed Tomography for Radiotherapy: SynthRAD2023 Challenge Report. arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.08447. 2024 Mar 13.

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Chandarana, H., Wang, H., Tijssen, R. H. N., Das, I. J. (2018). Emerging role of MRI in radiation therapy. *Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging*, 48(6), 1468-1478. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmri.26271>

Chernak E.S., Rodriguez-Antunez A., Jelden G.L., Dhaliwal R.S., Lavik P.S. The use of computed tomography for radiation therapy treatment planning. *Radiology*. 1975 Dec;117(3):613-4. <https://doi.org/10.1148/117.3.613>

Giacometti, V., Hounsell, A. R., McGarry, C. K. (2020). A review of dose calculation approaches with cone beam CT in photon and proton therapy. *Physica Medica*, 76, 243-276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmp.2020.06.017>

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Legendijk, J. J., Raaymakers, B. W., Van den Berg, C. A., Moerland, M. A., Philippens, M. E., Van Vulpen, M. (2014). MR guidance in radiotherapy. *Physics in Medicine & Biology*, 59(21), R349.

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Edmund, J. M., Nyholm, T. (2017). A review of substitute CT generation for MRI-only radiation therapy. *Radiation Oncology*, 12(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13014-016-0747-y>

Kurz, C., Buizza, G., Landry, G., Kamp, F., Rabe, M., Paganelli, C., Baroni, G., Reiner, M., Keall P. J., van den Berg, C. A. T., Riboldi, M. (2020). Medical physics challenges in clinical MR-guided radiotherapy. *Radiation Oncology*, 15, 93. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13014-020-01524-4>

Spadea, M. F. & Maspero, M., Zaffino, P., Seco, J. (2021). Deep learning-based synthetic-CT generation in radiotherapy and PET: A review. *Medical Physics*, 48(11), 6537-6566. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mp.15150>

For the data pre-processing

Schwarz, C. G., Kremers, W. K., Wiste, H. J., Gunter, J. L., Vemuri, P., Sychalla, A. J., ... & Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative. (2021). Changing the face of neuroimaging research: Comparing a new MRI de-facing technique with popular alternatives. *NeuroImage*, 231, 117845.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2021.117845>

For the metrics

Low, D.A., Harms, W.B., Mutic, S., and Purdy, J.A. (1998), A technique for the quantitative evaluation of dose distributions. *Med. Phys.*, 25: 656-661. <https://doi.org/10.1118/1.598248>

Hall, W. A., Paulson, E., Davis, B. J., Spratt, D. E., Morgan, T. M., Dearnaley, D., ... & Lawton, C. A. (2021). NRG oncology updated international consensus atlas on pelvic lymph node volumes for intact and postoperative prostate cancer. *International Journal of Radiation Oncology* Biology* Physics*, 109(1), 174-185.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrobp.2020.08.034>

Lambrecht, M., Eekers, D. B., Alapetite, C., Burnet, N. G., Calugaru, V., Coremans, I. E., ... & Troost, E. G. (2018). Radiation dose constraints for organs at risk in neuro-oncology; the European Particle Therapy Network consensus. *Radiotherapy and Oncology*, 128(1), 26-36 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radonc.2018.05.001>

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Marks LB, Yorke ED, Jackson A, Ten Haken RK, Constone LS, Eisbruch A, Bentzen SM, Nam J, Deasy JO. Use of normal tissue complication probability models in the clinic. *International Journal of Radiation Oncology* Biology* Physics*. 2010 Mar 1;76(3):S10-9.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

Given the restricted format of the online submission form available at

<https://www.biomedical-challenges.org/miccai2025-lighthouse-challenges>, e.g., no tables/figures and not even symbols or possibilities to add bullets to the forms, we have provided a decently formatted template in the supplementary material.